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Influence Of Continuous Assessment On The Academic Performance Of NCE II Students Of Federal College Of Education Gidan Madi, Sokoto State

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ABSTRACT

The paper focused on the influence of Continuous Assessment on the Academic Performance of NCE II Students of Federal College of Education Gidan Madi, Sokoto State. The researchers employed a descriptive research of survey type, with all the one hundred and fifty three (153) NCE II students across fourteen (14) departments in the three (3) schools at FCE Gidan Madi as population. The population of one hundred and fifty three (153) NCE II students and they are also selected as sample. Researchers' designed instrument titled; continuous assessment questionnaire (CAQ) was used in collecting data. Data was collected on direct delivery techniques in administration and collection of the completed questionnaires. Frequency, Percentages and chi-square statistics were used in analyzing the data. After the analysis the results indicated that; Essay, Multiple Choice, and Assignment are the most commonly continuous assessment techniques used by lecturers of FCE Gidan Madi, Sokoto state, there is significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General education Courses and General studies Courses. Finally conclusion and recommendations were made to include; Directorate of guidance and counselling and career service centre of FCE Gidan Madi should organize a regular training of lecturers on the application of Continuous assessment methods in evaluating the students.

Keywords: Continuous assessment, Academic, Performance, NCE students

INTRODUCTION

Assessment of learning is not one time movement, it is a progressing process. It includes the procedure of checking on, reflecting and modifying the learning techniques in an arranged and cautious way. Results of assessment are useful for decisions making and in providing information on the degree to which a particular course or subject has benefited the students (Onihunwa et al., 2018). Assessment is a method in which learner achievement is measured (Azzah, 2015). Assessment is used to make a decision on the achievement of students. It is a very important process as the process of teaching itself (Iljazi, 2013). What is relevant for students is explained by assessment and how they will see themselves as learners.

The assessment is referred to as continuous assessment when it is applied as a continuous procedure. It is to assess students overall progress regarding the ability, expertise and attitude after a given collection of experiences in learning. It contains several questions that are given to students during class, such as short questions, home assignments and re-cape exercises. It is based on learners' previous classroom performance levels. In addition, it allows teachers to figure out what the students have learned ([Abejehu, 2016](#)).

Continuous assessment is considered to be a method of evaluating what children benefit from schools in terms of skills, character development and business, taking into account all their success in oral or written examinations, assignments and other educational activities during that time. According to ([Azzah, 2015](#)) in all schools, continuous assessment is carried out as a formative assessment to educate teachers and students about the success of learners in enhancing learning. It is considered as a holistic approach to learning in its entirety, beginning with the decision on the success of teachers at initial entry in school and finishing with the decision taken by managers and teachers to learners on the end of the month, term and year ranking & up-gradation ([Allida & Basome, 2018](#)). Students reacted favourably to the continued use of the tests and found that student success was directly linked to student engagement. It is also necessary to understand that increased engagement is a way of improving the level of student experience and ensuring evaluations that enable students to engage with learning. Similarly, the success of a pupil is measured by comparing the performance of others to the same criteria used in the standard-referred evaluation.

When assessment is carried out in classroom in an ongoing or continual way by the teacher, it is called continuous assessment ([Samiullah & Anjum, 2017](#)). In this process, observations are made time to time to collect data to determine the level of students' knowledge, understanding and performance. It is done by giving particular tasks to students based on their previous achievement in classroom. Teacher observes the activities of students to decide about the level of their performance in class.

It also helps them to find out what the learners have learnt. Continuous assessment is part and parcel of instructional process that has to be taken as a key tool in educational quality assurance endeavor ([Abejehu, 2016](#)). [Airasian](#) as cited in [Samiullah and Anjum\(2017\)](#) reported that continuous assessment as an approach should present the complete number of sources and methods that teacher can apply to collect, interpret and synthesize information about students. The use of this information also helps teachers to understand their students, plan and monitor their teaching to create a feasible culture. [Baker and Stets](#) as cited in [Samiullah and Anjum, \(2017\)](#) stated that continuous assessment should include a regular assessment of students' affective structures and motivation in which they will need to express their determination intensely, their work force readiness and their skills in team or group performance background.

One of the most important and significant developments in Nigerian educational system was the introduction of the use of Continuous Assessment (CA) in evaluation of pupils and students in at all levels of schooling. By implication, every teacher from primary to secondary level of education should understand and practice Continuous Assessment. The emphasis on continuous assessment is not limited to Nigeria alone; other African countries notably Kenya, Zambia, Ghana, and Liberia have adopted the same policy. National Policy on Education (NPE) (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014) observed that the existing practice (in most institutions of learning) of basing the assessment of students work on final examination and on one-short examination only is no longer tenable.

In recent years, assessment practices in education have been subjected to critical review. Just as views about the nature of learning and educational practice have led to reappraisal of teaching and learning in schools, so there has been a need for an examination of how these are assessment help in improving the academic performance of students. Academic performance implies the outcome education, it is the extent to which the student, teacher or institution have their educational goals. In the words of ([Salihu & Abubakar, 2020](#)) academic performance is the ability to study and remember facts and being able to communicate one's knowledge verbally or written on paper. Academic performance is of two types i.e. positive (high) and negative (poor) performance. Poor academic performance as adjudged by the

examiner and some significant others are performance falling below an expected standards (Sadler, 2017). Gipps and Murphy as cited in Adeyemi (2008) view the increasing importance of assessment not only for pupils, but for the educational system as whole.’ Assessment may be defined as any method used to better understand the current knowledge that a student possesses. This implies that assessment can be as simple as a teacher’s subjective judgment based on a single observation of student performance, or as complex as a five-hour standardized test. The idea of current knowledge implies that what a student knows is always changing and that we can make judgment about student achievement through comparisons over a period of time. Assessment may affect decisions about grades, advancement, placement, instructional needs, and curriculum.

Assessment is often seen as serving three purposes for the teacher: measuring attainment, identifying strengths and weaknesses, and indicating progress or deterioration. However, assessment is also one way by which injustice can be avoided in education. If identifiable groups persistently attain a low level of intelligence or achievement and eventually leave school without being employed, while other similarly identifiable groups aspire higher in their education and get promising jobs, then any technique that promises the early identification of strengths and weaknesses also offer the chance of doing something early enough in school careers to provide beneficial effect of improving the overall performance of the students. Of great concern to the investigator have been several classrooms teaching observed as a part of monitoring team in some secondary schools over the past decade which reveal a grossly inadequate application of various mode of assessment in schools.

In Nigerian tertiary institutions, CA was recognised as a tool that was frequently used by lecturers and the school management in analysing students’ performance (Shukla, 2019). The purpose of CA was pointed out by Shukla (2019) a way of enhancing students’ learning, improving teachers’/lecturers’ teaching skills and improving the assessment system of institutions. The introduction of CA into the educational system of any country improves the use of formative evaluation in which recommended that there should be thorough supervision of the CA, all process must be monitored in Nigerian Universities for quality assurance.

Also, in higher institutions of learning in Nigeria formative assessments (continuous assessments) are conducted by lecturers within semesters when lectures are on-going while summative assessments (semester exams) are conducted at the end of semester. The totality of scores obtained in the formative and summative assessments are used to calculate the students’ grade point average. However, lecturers often find out that some students that perform well in the continuous assessments still have woeful performance in the semester exams. This might be due to the examination oriented education system in Nigeria which has persisted since inception of education. All the teaching and learning is centred on passing final examinations. It is sometimes referred to as “teaching to the test”. This challenge is compounded even further by the fact that students’ promotion or selection to another level is based on student’s grades.

Asaph (2020) believed that kind of assessment is subjective, informal, immediate, on-going, and intuitive as it interacts with learning as it occurs. The downside of this approach is that students are encouraged to exercise rote memorization of facts and cramming of information rather than acquiring problem-solving skills. This study was therefore conceived, designed and undertaken in order to analyse the various classroom assessment practice and find out influence of CA practices on the academic performance of NCE II students in Federal College of Education, Gidan Madi, Sokoto State.

Statement of the problem

At the tertiary education level, assessment process supposed to be continuous and progressive. The continuous assessment must be systematic, comprehensive, cumulative, and guidance oriented. The assessment supposed to bring out student’s progress and help educators to reflect on their performance, mastery and materials, endangering students’ idea and action, encourage students to ask questions and above all motivate them to learn. Assessment at school level, has a major role to play in the education of the learners because they spend the best of part of their lives with teachers and it is through the teacher’s assessment that their capabilities are better understood.

Furthermore, since the introduction of continuous assessment system by National Policy on Education in early 1980s, there are many challenges associated with its use in practice and implementation. In almost every year during processing of the Secondary Schools examination results, NECO and WAEC have identified an aspect of schools turning in high continuous assessment marks of their students which does not correlate at all with their respective final examination subjects marks. One would wonder why continuous assessment scores do not predict senior school certificate if continuous assessment is effectively conducted. Common to all these studies is the fact that continuous assessment allows for a diagnosis of the learners' learning difficulties. However, there are variations in the efficacy of the strategies adopted in the studies. In addition, some of the strategies are less applicable because of some obstacles inherent in mastery learning. Little has been done to determine effect of continuous assessment on high institutions students' performance.

Also, the purpose of continuous assessment is to assist in improving learning through administering of assignments and tests as the learning experiences increase before the end of term examination is taken. As good as the purpose for which CA was initiated, some lecturers/students in tertiary institutions complain of the drudgery of so many variant of structured and unstructured test and the lecturers see the conduct of so many tests as extra work and burden. As a result, the main purpose of continuous assessment is gradually being lost. It is in the light of this that, the researchers sought to investigate Influence of Continuous Assessment on the academic performance of NCE II Students in Federal College of Education Gidan Madi, Sokoto State, Nigeria.

Objectives

The objectives of this study are to find out;

1. The most commonly continuous assessment techniques employment for NCE II students of FCE Gidan Madi, Sokoto State.
2. The influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General Education Courses.
3. The influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General Studies Courses.

Research Questions

1. What are the most commonly continuous assessment techniques employment for NCE II of FCE Gidan Madi, Sokoto State?
2. What are the influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General Education Courses?
3. What are the influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General Studies Courses?

Hypotheses

1. There is no significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General Education Courses.
2. There is no significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General Studies Courses.

METHODOLOGY

The researcher employed a descriptive research of survey type, with all the one hundred and fifty three (153) NCE II students across fourteen (14) department in the three (3) schools at FCE Gidan Madi as population. The entire population of one hundred and fifty three (153) NCE II students were purposively selected as sample in the study. Researchers' designed instrument titled: continuous assessment questionnaire (CAQ) was used in collecting data for this study. CAQ consists of three (3) parts, part A Bio-data of the respondents, part B with ten (10) items on most commonly forms of continuous assessment used, part C with fifteen (15) items about Continuous assessment Then NCE GPA was used to measure students' academic performance

The Questionnaire assumed the four-point modified Likert scales of Most applicable, Applicable, not applicable and none at all with four (4), three (3), two (2) and one (1) as the score value of the Likert scale. The content validity of the instrument was obtained after scrutiny and correction of the test items by some experts in Guidance and Counselling and sociology of education at faculty of education and also some experts economics at the faculty of social sciences, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto and some lecturers at Sokoto state university, Sokoto and adjudged the instruments to have content and face validity. The reliability of the instruments was obtained using split-half method by administering the instruments to fifty (50) NCE students at SSCO, Sokoto and splitting the test scores into even and odd numbers and analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient that yielded 0.72, 0.75 and 0.79 reliability indexes. The data was collected on direct delivery techniques in administration and collection of the completed questionnaires. Frequency, Percentages and chi-square statistics was used in analyzing the data generated for the study.

RESULTS

Table 1: frequency and percentage of the most commonly C.A Techniques

RANK	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
Multiple Choice	34	22.2%
Essay	42	27.5%
Fill in the Blank	11	7.2%
Assignment	28	18.3%
True/False	09	5.9%
Yes/No	06	3.9%
Presentation	18	11.8%
Matching types	05	3.2%
TOTAL	153	100%

Source: Field Work September, 2025.

From the analysis of table 1, on the frequency and percentages of the respondents' base on the most commonly continuous assessment (C.A) techniques employed by the lecturers, the results indicated that respondents who employed Multiple Choice are 34 representing 22.2%, Essay are 42 representing 27.5%, Fill in the Blank are 11 representing 7.2%, Assignment are 28 representing 18.3%, True or False are 07 representing 5.9%, Yes/No are 06 representing 3.9%, Presentation are 18 representing 11.8% as well as those who employed matching types are 05 representing 3.2%, this indicated that respondents who employed Essay, Multiple Choice and Assignment are more represented in the study, meaning Essay, Multiple Choice and Assignment are the most commonly continuous assessment techniques used by lecturers of FCE Gidan Madi.

Hypothesis one: There is no significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General Education Courses.

Table 2: influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General Education Courses.

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Chi-Cal	p-Value	Decision
C A	153	17.74	5.211	.321	.000	H ₀ Rejected
Acad. Perf. In GE	153	18.40	5.902			

Source: Field Work September, 2025.

From result of Table 2, continuous assessment on the academic performance were positively related and significant, chi (153) = .321, $p = .000$. This indicates significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II because the p -value is less than the .05 level of significance.

Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General Education Courses was rejected.

Hypothesis two: There is no significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General studies Courses.

Table 3: influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General studies courses

Variables	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t-Cal	p-Value	Decision
C A	153	18.48	5.103	.135	.001	H ₀ Rejected
Acad. Perf. in GS	153	18.40	4.987			

Source: Field Work July, 2024.

From result of table 3, continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General studies courses were positively related and significant, $\chi^2(153) = .135, p = .001$. This indicates significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General studies courses because the p -value is less than the .05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that there is no significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General studies Courses was rejected.

Summary of major findings

1. Essay, Multiple Choice, and Assignment are the most commonly continuous assessment techniques used by lecturers of FCE Gidan Madi, Sokoto state.
2. There is significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General education Courses.
3. There is significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General studies Courses.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

From the analysis of the descriptive data of the respondents it can be seen that, frequency and percentages of the respondents' base most commonly continuous assessment techniques employed by lecturers at FCE Gidan Madi, the results indicated that respondents who employed Multiple Choice are 34 representing 22.2%, Essay are 42 representing 27.5%, Fill in the Blank are 11 representing 7.2%, Assignment are 28 representing 18.3%, True or False are 07 representing 5.9%, Yes/No are 06 representing 3.9%, Presentation are 18 representing 11.8% as well as those who employed matching types are 05 representing 3.2%, this indicated that respondents who employed Essay, Multiple Choice and Assignment are more represented in the study, this results signified that, Essay, Multiple Choice and Assignment are the most commonly continuous assessment techniques used by lecturers of FCE Gidan Madi.

Based on the hypothesis one which states that, There is no significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General Education Courses, the results shows that, continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General Education Courses were positively related and significant, calculated $\chi^2(153) = .321, p = .000$. This indicates significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General Education Courses because the p -value is less than the .05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis was rejected. This finding agree with previously existing studies for example; Samiullah and Anjum, (2017) stated that continuous assessment should include a regular assessment of students' affective structures and motivation in which they will need to express their determination intensely, their work force readiness and their skills in team or group performance background. in higher institutions of learning in Nigeria formative assessments (continuous assessments) are conducted by lecturers within semesters when lectures are on-going while summative assessments (semester exams) are conducted at the end of semester. The totality of scores obtained in the formative and summative assessments are used

to calculate the students' grade point average. However, lecturers often find out that some students that perform well in the continuous assessments still have woeful performance in the semester exams. One of the most important and significant developments in Nigerian educational system was the introduction of the use of Continuous Assessment (CA) in evaluation of pupils and students in at all levels of schooling. By implication, every teacher from primary to secondary level of education should understand and practice Continuous Assessment.

Based on the analysis of data of hypothesis two which states that; there is no significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General studies Courses, the results shows that continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General studies Courses were positively related and significant, because calculated chi (153) = .135, $p = .001$. This indicates significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General studies Courses because the p -value is less than the .05 level of significance. Therefore, the hypothesis was rejected and the finding agree with other existing studies for example; Shukla (2019) stated that C. A is a way of enhancing students' learning, improving teachers'/lecturers' teaching skills and improving the assessment system of institutions. The introduction of CA into the educational system of any country improves the use of formative evaluation in which recommended that there should be thorough supervision of the CA, all process must be monitored in Nigerian Universities for quality assurance. Assessment is often seen as serving three purposes for the teacher: measuring attainment, identifying strengths and weaknesses, and indicating progress or deterioration. However, assessment is also one way by which injustice can be avoided in education.

CONCLUSION

Conclusion drawn from the outcome of this study indicated that; respondents who employed Essay, Multiple Choice and Assignment are more represented in the study. There is significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General Education Courses and there is significant influence of continuous assessment on the academic performance of NCE II students in General studies Courses. This means that continuous assessment techniques employed by lecturers of FCE Gidan Madi contributed to the NCE students positive academic performance as well as class room related interactions both within and outside the class room environment.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Directorate of guidance and counselling and career service centre of FCE Gidan Madi should organize a regular training of lecturers on the application of Continuous assessment methods in evaluating the students.
2. FCE Gidan Madi management should partners with all the stakeholders in training and re-training as well as acquisitions of basic continuous assessment tools and materials for usage and implementation of NCE curriculum so as to boost students' performance across all aspects.
3. Colleges of Education Academic Staff Union (COEASU) should also should also partner with other clubs, societies and associations in creating and implementing continuous professional development programme geared towards equipping lecturers with 21st century skills of teaching and evaluating NCE students.

REFERENCES

- Abejehu, S. B. (2016). The practice of continuous assessment in primary schools: The case of Chagni, Ethiopia. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(13): 7-10.
- Adeyemi, B. A. (2008). Enhancing academic excellence in social studies through authentic assessment and portfolio assessment. *International Journal of African & African American Studies*, 7(1): 34-42.

- Allida, V. & Basome S. (2018). The influence of continuous assessment on academic performance in primary schools of Ibulanku sub-county, Iganga district (Uganda). *Baraton Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 8(Special Issue), 1-7.
- Asaph, A. (2020). *Impact of Continuous Assessment on Pupils' Academic Performance in Primary Schools in Kabale Municipality, Kabale District* (Doctoral dissertation, Kabale University).
- Azzah, A. (2015). Comparison between continuous assessment and final examination scores. *Quality Management & Enhancement in Higher Education. Conference proceedings, Muscat*, 1-13.
- Federal Republic of Nigeria (2014). National Policy on Education. Abuja: NERDC.
- Iljazi, T. (2013). *Continuous assessment develops thinking skills, quality of learning and teaching*. Conference Proceedings, National Academy of Science review. 61-68.
- Onihunwa, J., Adigun, O. Irunokhai, E., Sada, Y., Jeje, A., Adeyemi, O & Adesina, O. (2018). Roles of Continuous Assessment Scores in Determining the Academic Performance of Computer Science Students in Federal College of Wildlife Management. *American Journal of Engineering Research (AJER)*, 7(5). 7-21. <https://www.ajer.org/>.
- Sadler, D. R. (2017). Assuring academic achievement standards: from moderation to calibration. In *International teacher judgement practices* (pp. 15-29). Routledge.
- Salihu, J. J. A., & Abubakar, I. D. (2020). Effects of educational field trips on social studies students' academic achievement in junior secondary schools in Kaduna State, Nigeria. *Education, Sustainability and Society*, 3(2), 41-44.
- Samiullah, I. M. & Anjum, A. (2017). Effect of continuous assessment techniques on students' performance at elementary level. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, 39(1): 91-100.
- Shukla, A. (2019). Continuous assessment features and purpose. <https://www.toppr.com/bytes/continuousassessment-features-and-purpose/amp/>